
INFLUENCE OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT ON EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF OF OSUN, STATE, UNIVERSITY, OSOGBO: MODERATING ROLE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE

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Abstract

Most organizations are passing through the faces that endeared them to liquidity due to limited investment in human capital with implications on employee performance and productivity. In fact, literature revealed that the business world is experiencing systemic failures that have affected the job performance of the employees in workplaces (Etu-Menson, 2011). The study therefore, investigate the influence of training and development on employee job performance: moderating role of leadership style (transformational leadership, Transactional leadership), among academic staff in Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The targeted population of the study comprises of 431 academic staff of Osun State University. The study made use of proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select the respondents. Three research instrument, Training and Development Questionnaire (TDQ), the Employee's job Performance Questionnaire (EJPQ) and

Moderating Role of Leadership Style Questionnaire (MRLSQ), were validated, and their reliability was ascertained. Three research questions were raised, and three hypotheses were formulated and analyzed with inferential statistics. The findings established that there was a significant combined contribution of training and development, relationship between Training and Development and leadership Style is statistically significant as $P\text{-value} < 0.05$, a very strong and positive relative contribution exists between training and development and leadership style. The study recommended that the employee training programmes need to be taken into consideration by giving them opportunities to learn new ideas and skills, in order to have more productive outcomes. However, the study concluded that Osun State University Osogbo has invested in the training of its employees, however the management needs to look into the various training programmes which are yet to be taken into cognizance.

Keywords:

Training, Development, Employee, Leadership, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of employees is crucial for both organizations and individuals; the role that these employees play in boosting an organization's productivity cannot be overemphasized (Baig et al., 2021). Thus, employees are the most essential resource for every organization, and their productivity has a significant impact on the performance of the organization (Khassawneh et al., 2023). Employee Job Performance is crucial because employees provide essential services to the public, such as educational services in public educational institutions, healthcare services in public hospitals, and other transactions in public organizations (Somani, 2021). Consequently, the public sector is an essential component of the nation's economy and plays a crucial role in generating employment and providing high-quality public services (Qing & JinHua, 2023). As a result, employees are working longer hours while feeling more anxious and less fulfilled in their work, which reduces their productivity, and increases the rate of absenteeism and the desire to quit their jobs (Ravina-Ripoll et al., 2019).

In the recent times, most organizations are passing through the faces that endeared them to liquidity due to limited investment in human capital with implications on job performance and productivity. In fact, literature revealed that the business world is experiencing systemic failures that have affected the job performance of the employees in workplaces (Etu-Menson, 2011).

Such employee's performance deficiencies are the product of fraud, theft, negligence, environmental hazards, and human error risk factors Barth, (Carprio & Levine, 2008). Such activities include business risk, human capital, and oversight of management. Risk caused by uncertainty can affect business performance either positively or negatively (Project Management Institute (PMI), 2008). The collapse of these institutions affected investors, shareholders, professionals, and academicians in their understanding and practices of operational risk management (Bamahros & Bhasin, 2016). According to Wurim (2012), where employees are not well managed, organizations will be confronted with the problems of over or under staffing, inability to attract and retain the people required and difficulty in the development and training of highly talented personnel.

The notion of training and development has been defined by various scholars from different disciplines. Obadahun, et al, (2022), define training and development as “learning experiences designed to enhance the short-term and/or long-term job performance of individual employees. According to Nurlitaet al. (2022), "training and development is a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge, or skill behavior through learning experience to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities. It's a continuous process of development aimed at connecting workers' abilities and expertise to the goals of the company (Bohorquez, 2022).

Al-Amin and Jeni (2021). Previously said, the main goals of training and development are to improve an employee's knowledge and abilities as well as their attitudes or perspectives toward the accomplishment of corporate objectives. Chanana (2021) asserts that training boosts workers' self-esteem, recognition, and increasing responsibility with the potential for compensation increases, all of which contribute to employee motivation. It also decreases cost of production since well trained personnel is able to make better economic use of materials and equipment hence decreasing waste if not eliminating it.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that most organization could not recognize the value of employees in driving the organizations towards organizational goal achievement. Employees has been described as the most valued asset in work organization (Akintayo et al., 2020), and thus required the attention of the employers of labour especially in upskilling and reskilling them in preparation for job performance. The negligence on the part of organizations had often led to dearth of competence on the part of employees, which has been responsible for poor job performance, low productivity and possibly liquidity crisis. It is pertinent to note that employees' job performance is enhanced by having the right human capital amidst proper management control with appropriate skills and competence to achieve favourable organizational goals and objectives (Bamahros & Bhasin, 2016). In essence, failure on the part of the employers to train their workforce often resulted to poor job performance which could hinder organizational goal achievement. This procedure is needed to address the internal failure of processes, systems as a result of weakness from external events, training and management control (Ragian et al., 2014). However, some researchers had conducted studies on the relationship between training and development and employees\ job performance but had reported conflicting findings. Some researcher reported that training and development has significantly influence employees' job satisfaction and performance while some reported negative relationship among the variables investigated. This conflicting findings therefore required further empirical verification for possible generalization of the findings. Most importantly, improving the quality and relevance of employee may help organizations to better understand and appraise their overall people-related strengths and weaknesses and identify areas for improvement.

Against this foregoing, this study is designed to investigate the influence of training and development on employees; job performance in Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of the study was to investigate the influence of training and development on employees' job performance. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. examine the combined contribution of training and development to employees' job performance.
- ii. determine the relative contribution of training and development to employees' job performance.
- iii. ascertain the relationship between training, development and employees' job performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated for the study:

- i. What is the combined contribution of training and development to employees' job performance?
- ii. What is the relative contribution of training and development to employees' job performance?
- iii. What is the pattern of relationship between training, development and job performance?

Hypotheses for the Study

The following hypotheses were generated for the study:

- H₁: There is no significant combined contribution of training and development to employee job performance
- H₂: There is no significant relative contribution of training and development to employee job performance.
- H₃: There is no significant relationship between training, development and job performance.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Employee Performance

The performance of employees is crucial for both organizations and individuals. The significance of this performance stems from the role that these employees play in boosting an organization's productivity (Baig et al., 2021). Thus, employees are the most essential resource for every organization, and their productivity has a significant impact on the performance of the organization (Khassawneh et al., 2023). EP is defined as the quality and quantity of work results to be attained by an employee in carrying out their responsibilities and duties (Siswanti & Astuti, 2020).

(Qing & JinHua, 2023). Contrary to this belief, the majority of prior research has focused on the performance of employees in the private sector, whereas only a few have examined this performance in the public sector (Tran & Pham, 2018). In a production-driven economy,

organizations encourage employees to improve their performance. As a result, employees are working longer hours while feeling more anxious and less fulfilled in their work, which reduces their productivity, and increases the rate of absenteeism and the desire to quit their jobs (Ravina-Ripoll et al., 2019).

According to Warella et al. (2021) stated that performance is the result of work achieved by an employee in a certain period according to the main tasks and functions that have been determined based on applicable regulations in order to achieve organizational goals. According to Nailufar (2012), performance can be defined as the work of an individual or organization that can be accomplished in line with authority and duty in the pursuit of officially achieving organizational goals, that does not break the law and that does not contradict with morals and ethics. Work performance and outcomes achieved by a person, in the form of goods or products as well as services, which are typically used as the foundation for evaluating the employee or work organization concerned, and which show the individual's knowledge of the job, are referred to as performance (Fauzi, 2020).

Training and Development

These days, training and advancement are an exceptionally huge factor in the business world since for upgrading the productivity and the viability of both employees and the organization. Khan and Khan (2011) and Noe (2001) stated that organizations that take on training and advancement rehearses can hold their clients, providers, workers, investors, and different partners over the long haul as they are considered more reliable and better overseers of the interests of the different partners. Biswas (2012) contended that Training and improvement are the pieces of the human asset advancement work. Training and advancement play a significant part in addressing the hole between current performance and anticipated future performance of the workers (Weil and Woodall, 2005; Sims, 2002). Training focuses on current jobs while development prepare employees for possible future jobs. Basically, the training and development plans to improve the association's general objective (Armstrong, 2003). Characterizes the training and development is a deliberate cycle planned by the organization to further develop the current and future worker performance by expanding a employee's abilities, information and capacity to perform through learning activities, changing the employee's mentality and conduct.

Employee Training as a source of Competency

Employees that receive training can do their jobs with greater competence and effectiveness. Positive changes in an employee's competency level are brought about by effective training programs. The Ahmad group (2019). According to Burhan et al. (2021), businesses can also meet the needs of their employees through training and development programs. According to Akilandeswari (2022), efficient training programs assist staff members in obtaining new technology that facilitates their work performance while also giving them complete control over the competencies and skills necessary to complete that specific task with fewer errors and blunders.

Employee Training as a source of Productivity.

The assertion made by Hammond and Churchill (2022) that training is a basic and effective tool in the successful fulfillment of the firm's goal and objectives, leading to higher production, is that timely and suitable training helps to increase organizational productivity. According to Downes (2022), there is a positive correlation between staff productivity and well-designed training programs.

Employee training as a source of motivation factor

Training is one of the most important things that an organization can do to motivate its employees. According to Kaung San (2019), when employees receive sufficient and relevant training that inspires them and guides them toward meeting their needs, they typically perform better. According to Obadahun et al. (2022), a business that prioritizes employee training and development together with providing them with competitive rewards for their achievements can enhance employee motivation and loyalty.

Employee Training Increase job of Satisfaction

Bohorquez (2022) emphasized that a variety of characteristics, including management, expertise, and job happiness, are protective of employee performance. According to Nurlita et al. (2022), trained and developed workers are happier in their jobs, which boosts an organization's productivity and profitability. According to Rampa et al. (2021), employees who receive training exhibit improved performance and a higher degree of job satisfaction.

Theoretical Review

Human Capital Theory

The human capital of the organization comprises all qualities and professional skills the worker brings into the organization. According to Resource-based View Theory (RBV), a firm can maximize its competitive advantage through its human resources characterized by rare, inimitable, valuable, non-substitutable and non-tradable (Agyabeng-Mensah and Tang, 2021). Therefore, HC, which involves intangible assets of employees in terms of knowledge, experience, capabilities, skills, creativities, genetic inheritance, and commitments altogether, can direct towards environmental protection and then ES (Sugiyanto and Febrianti, 2021; Chang and Chen, 2012; Chen, 2008).

In this regard, Yadiati *et al.* (2019) appreciated the critical role of HC to meet the objectives of sustainable development through the implementation of green corporate practices. Therefore, HC plays a crucial role as a driving force for structural capital (SC) and relational capital (RC) (Sabbir and Taufique, 2021; Chahal and Bakshi, 2014). Moreover, employees, who have more extraordinary skills and knowledge of activities help in improving the efficiencies through reduction of waste, cost, and consumption, and this ensures achieving OP because HC considers a vital strategic resource for a sustainable competitive edge in today's age of ever-changing environment (Yusliza *et al.*, 2020; Mas, 2019). Little is known about the processes by which HRM practices lead employees to behave eco-friendly despite GHRM practices positively

influence green employee behaviour because GHC involves intangible assets such as knowledge, skills, capabilities, creativities, wisdom, experience, attitude, and commitments of employees, which are essential for achieving BS in the current competitive market environment (Cahyono & Hakimn, 2020; Yusliza *et al.*, 2020; Kim *et al.*, 2019).

Herzberg Two Factor Theory

Herzberg (1959) developed a two dimensional model of the variables influencing people's perspectives about their jobs. He came to the conclusion that variables like pay, working environment, supervision, interpersonal relationships, and corporate policy are more of hygienic considerations than motivators. Giannis Peramatzis (2022). The hypothesis states that while the presence of hygienic variables does not inspire or promote satisfaction, their lack can lead to job discontent.

Herzberg distinguished between elements that are external to the job and internal to motivation. Therefore, although hygiene aspects assist to lessen job dissatisfaction, motivation factors only serve to enhance and boost job happiness. As stated by Herzberg and colleagues (1959). but other employment aspects mitigate disillusionment. According to Herzberg, "No fulfilment" is the inverse of "fulfilment" and "No dissatisfaction" is the inverse of "disappointment." These activity variables were divided into two categories by Herzberg: inspiration factors and cleaning elements.

Yousaf (2020) asserts that the theory of Herzberg employee motivation is highly relevant in understanding the work behaviors of organizational employees. However, this theory has faced significant criticism from those who vehemently argue that the original theory should not be revived because it has little bearing on the explanation of employee motivation. As Khan and Zaki (2017) have noted, employees are a firm's most valuable resource, with the power to either enhance or diminish its corporate and business standing through their impact on overall profitability (Elnaga and Imran, (2018).

Empirical Review

According to Almazrouei *et al.* (2022), an investigation achieving optimal employee JOB performance is not a random process but rather a deliberate process involving a number of tactics, with training and development taking center stage. Furthermore, according to Downes (2022), employee training refers to planned activities intended to increase staff awareness, experience, and expertise. employees to do their best efforts.

Likewise, Ahmad *et al.* (2019) have clarified that skilled workers are more competent and perform their duties more effectively than unskilled workers. Training and development are urgently needed in a developing nation like Pakistan and would boost the telecom industry's efficacy. Training is one of the primary human resource activities in an organization and aids in the achievement of organizational goals, according to Burhan *et al.* (2021). Additionally, Salaset *al.* (2021) state that the knowledge, skills, and capacities of employees are becoming more and more crucial for the organization as well as for the individual employee. It is crucial that these

personnel receive training and development in order for them to acquire new abilities and information that will enhance their effectiveness as employees.

According to Al-Sharafi et al. (2018), businesses that offer training and development programmes help programmers keep their competitive edge. These businesses also benefit from motivated employees who are more likely to stick with the company. According to Bello et al. (2021), one approach to think about training is as a subsystem that introduces staff members to the subject matter and technology because organizations are always evolving and growing. Employee development and training is even more important in the modern era, when globalization has increased organizational competitiveness and made it harder for workers to keep up with the rate of technological improvement and other scientific and social advancements. Churchill and Hammond (2018).

Job Description and Employee Performance

The utilization of skillfully crafted job description (JD) can aid managers in enhancing work performance and fostering job satisfaction (Khtatbeh et al., 2020; Ramhit, 2019). As per the findings of several scholars, JD encompass a diverse range of details such as job designations, organizational and departmental identification, mandatory and suggested qualifications and job responsibilities. Furthermore, the JD delineates the requisite qualifications and the requisite physical conditioning for the position. JD is a crucial component for organizations (Sembiring & Normi, 2021; Setyoko, 2020). AL Rawas & Jantan, Cogent Business & Management (2023).

Transformational Leadership as a Moderating Variable

The direct effect of TFL was examined in several studies (Fan et al., 2023; Khassawneh & Elrehail, 2022; Sarwar et al., 2023). However, when it comes to the moderating effect of this variable, there are limited studies especially in the context of public sector. Lee and Wei (2017) examined the moderating effects of TFL and found that it moderated the effect of interactional justice and affective commitment. Ugheoke (2019) found that TFL moderated positively the effect of organizational culture on employee performance in Oman. In China, Sungu et al. (2019) found that TFL moderated positively the impact of organizational commitment on job performance. Cobbinah et al. (2020) also found that TFL moderated the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. Moderating effect of transactional leadership: The transactional leader employs a leader-follower interaction. Employees are rewarded for their exceptional performance, while leaders profit from greater organizational performance and employee task completion. TSL considers employee performance will improve based on the reward provided (Bass, 2019).

The transactional leader defines staff duties and rewards. Transactional leaders think their followers are logical, and motivated by rewards and incentives. Followers are predictable. Transactional leaders are efficient, focused on the present, and can improve the organization as a whole. TSL is a contingency reward, management by exception, and passive/active leadership (Bass, 2019). Prior studies investigated the direct effect of TSL on employee performance (Amalina & Susilowati, 2022; Jamali et al., 2020). Moderating effect of TSL has been examined in a few studies (Arumugam et al., 2019; Cobbinah et al., 2020, Haryanto et al., 2022; Lee &

Wei, 2017; Sungu et al., 2019; Ugheoke, 2020). Munawar et al. (2021) found that TSL moderated positively the effect of corporate social responsibility on organizational performance. In Oman, leaders who links the rewards and pay to the adherence of rules, duties, and responsibility can lead employees to follow their JD and results in a positive increase in employee performance. Therefore, this paper proposed that TSL moderates the effect of JD on employee performance.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the method and procedures that were used in carrying out the study. These include: research design, study area, population, sample and sampling techniques, method of data collection, research instrument, procedure for data collection, administration of the instrument, method of data analysis and makes specification of variables.

Research design

A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The research design is appropriate for the study because it affords the researcher to collect data from the respondents without manipulation of any variable of interest. In terms of adequate representation, the research design also affords respondents of the equal chance of participation in the study. Besides, the research design is considered relevant in the study because a large amount of data was gathered for analysis and interpretation using the appropriate statistical methods to analyze the independent variable employee job performance and dependent variable training and development moderating role of leadership style.

Study Area

The geographical area for the study was Osun State University Osogbo, Osun State University has six campuses, namely, Osogbo Campus as academic and administrative unit, Okuku Campus, Ifetedo Campus, Ikire Campus, Ipetu Ijesa Campus and Ejigbo Campus. It serves as the focus of the study for data collection.

Population of the study

The population of the study comprises of four hundred and thirty one (431) academic staff in which forty one (41) are full Professors. The study therefore selected both senior and junior academic staff of which includes Professors, senior lecturers, and junior lecturers of Osun State University Osogbo. Osun State University Osogbo comprises of six satellite campuses, which are situated in (Osogbo college of health and Sciences, Okuku college of Management and Social Sciences, Ipetu Ijesha college of Education, Ikire college of Humanities and Culture, Ejigbo college of Agricultural Science, Ifetedo college of Law), respectively

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The section discussed the sample size and procedure which were utilized. To achieve a representative data from the population, the proportionate stratified sampling technique was used

to select the respondents to ensure that different groups of a population are adequately represented in the sample so as to increase their level of accuracy when estimating parameters.

Method of Data Collection

The study use primary and secondary data collection through administering questionnaires. The primary data was obtained using structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. Secondary data were sourced from official publications of the selected industries, textbooks, academic journals, periodic and internet library.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in gathering data for the study is structured questionnaire. The structured questionnaire consists of two (2) sections, which include: A, B and C.

Section A: This section contains the socio-demographic information about the respondents, which include: the name of industry, age, gender, marital status, highest educational qualification, position/rank and working experience, etc.

Section B: This section deals with information relating to training and development as it affects employees' job performance. The scale covers a standard, broad, spectrum and practical aspects of training and development. The questionnaire was measured on a 4-point Likert modified response rating scale, namely: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N) Disagree (D)and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Section C: This section deals with information relating to employees' job performance. The scale covers a standard, broad, spectrum and practical aspects of employees' job performance. The questionnaire was measured on a 4-point Likert modified response rating scale, namely: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N) Disagree (D)and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Analysis

The data from the questionnaire was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). hereinafter referred to as "PLS4" was used to test the research hypotheses constructed in this study. The relationships that emerge from the raw data was analyzed, interpreted, or explain using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1 There is no significant combined contribution of training and development to employees' job performance

Combined contribution of Training and Development to Employees’ Job Performance

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.664 ^a	.441	.440		.726

a. Predictors: (Constant), EP

Source: Author’s Computation using SPSS 23.0, (2024)

Table 2 shows the model summary of the regression analysis of interaction between strategic planning (Competency, Productivity and Motivation) and employee job performance with (R) value of .664^a. This indicates a strong association between Training and Development and employee job performance. R² value of 0.441 indicates that Training and development accounted for about 44% level of employee job performance among academic staffs at Osun State University, Osogbo. Other variables which that accounted for about 56% employee job Performance were not contained in this model but represented under the stochastic error term.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3190.439	1	3.320	.457	.001 ^b
	Residual	3.320	439	7.268		
	Total	3193.760	440			

a. Dependent Variable: TD

b. Predictors: (Constant), EP

Source: Author’s Computation using SPSS 23.0, (2025)

Table 3 shows the F-statistics value for regression to test the overall significance of the independent variables in explaining the Training and Development of the academic staffs at osun state University Osogbo. The result shows that Employee performance in the selected study area significantly predicted the level training and development with the F value. 303.76, P-value < 0.05 (Sig .000). This indicates strong evidence against null hypothesis, as there is less than 5% probability that null hypothesis is correct.

F – statistical indicates that the overall regression model is highly statistically significant in terms of its goodness of fit since the value of $F_{tab} (.303.76) > F_{cal} (.457)$. The Study therefore concluded that, Training and development has a significant influence on employee performance.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relative contribution of Training and Development to employee job Performance.

Relative contribution of Training and Development to Employee Job Performance.

Table 4.5: Analysis of the Interaction between Training and Development impact to employees’ job performance among academic staffs in Osun state university, Ososgbo

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.639 ^a	.409	.407	.746

a. Predictors: (Constant),LS

Source: Author’s Computation using SPSS 23.0, (2024)

Table 4.5 shows the model summary of the regression analysis of interaction between Training and development and leader style among academic staffs at Osun state University, Ososgbo with (R) value of .639^a. This indicates a strong association between training and development and Leadership Style. R² value of .409 indicates training and development account for about 41% level of leadership style. Other variables which accounted for about 59% are not contained in this model but represented under the stochastic error term.

Table 4.6 Regression Showing Significance training and development to leadership style among academic staffs at Osun State University, Osogbo

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3189.870	1	3.889	.535	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.889	439	7.266		
	Total	3193.760	440			

a. Dependent Variable: TD

b. Predictors: (Constant), LS

Source: Author’s Computation using SPSS 23.0, (2024)

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between training, development and job performance: the moderating role of leadership style.

Relationship between Training, Development and Employees’ Job Performance.

Table 4.7 showing the relationships between Training, Development and Job performance: the moderating role of leadership style

Correlations

		TD	EP	Development
TD	Correlation	1.000	.823	.702
	Significance (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
	Df	0	438	438
EP	Correlation	.823	1.000	.795
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
	df	438	0	438
Development	Correlation	.702	.795	1.000
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
	df	438	438	0

From table 4.7 Leadership Style was used for controlling the influence of all relationships (LS), all relationships show strong, statistically significant positive correlations:

4.3 Discussions of Findings

Objective one (examine the combine contribution of Training and Development (Competency, Productivity and Motivation) to employee job performance (Job description), a moderating role of leadership style (transformational leadership, Transactional leadership). This was achieved with the aid of hypothesis One. The major findings from this hypothesis tested are; a very strong association exist between combined integrated talent strategies and employee turnover intention. R^2 value = 0.441 revealed that 44% percent level of relationship exist among the variables captured. This means that combine contribution of training and development maintain strong positive relationship with employee performance among academic staffs at Osun State University, Osogbo

That the relationship between combined contribution of training and development is statistically significant as P-value < 0.05. Each of the variable is significant to employee performance. The finding established that there is significant combined contribution of training and development.

Objective five determine the relative contribution of Training and Development to employee job Performance), a moderating role of leadership style.

This was achieved with the aid of hypothesis two. From the finding, the following were established; a very strong and positive relative contribution exist between training and development and leadership style. R^2 value = 0.409, 41% percent level of association exist among the training and development and leadership style.

Also, relationship between Training and Development and leadership Style is statistically significant as P-value < 0.05. Each of the variable is significant to leadership style. The finding

established that there is significant relative contribution of training and development to leadership style. The finding of the study also establish that the employee performance was examined less in public sector compared to private sector. In the public sector, EP is crucial because employees provide essential services to the public, such as educational services in public educational institutions, healthcare services in public hospitals, and other transactions in public organizations (Somani, 2021). Therefore, the performance of employees in the public sector contributes to the sector and to the provision of essential public services to the country's citizens and other stakeholders (Hayati & Aviana, 2023). Contrary to this belief, the majority of prior research has focused on the performance of employees in the private sector, whereas only a few have examined this performance in the public sector (Tran & Pham, 2018).

The findings of this research indicated that the various training undergone in the selected institutions has impacted on employee performance but the management needs to look into the training package. Most of the employees were of the view that training and development were effective tools for both personal and organizational success.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the study showed that employees' job performance has significantly influenced by the different training programmes being organized for employees in Osun State University, Osogbo. The study established that training and development are important factors in the consideration of employees' job performance.

However, the study concluded that Osun state University Osogbo has invested in the training of its employees, however the management needs to look into the various training programmes for more efficiency and to facilitate improved performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings of the study:

The institution should show concern on training and development programmes that can facilitate improved performance on the part of employees with implications for efficient service delivery.

The management of the University should endeavour to ascertain the training needs of all staff for them to acquire the specific skill that are keenly related to efficient employees' service delivery in work organizations. The study recommended that the employee training programme need to take into consideration by given them opportunities to learn new ideas and skills to become more productive.

References

- Ahmad, A., Kura, K. M., Bibi, P., Khalid, N., & Rahman Jaaffar, A. (2019). Effect of compensation, training and development, and manager support on employee commitment. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(7), 20–36.
- Bamahros, H. M., & Bhasin, M. L. (2016). Audit committee characteristics and unexpected accruals: An empirical study of Malaysia. *Wulfenia Journal*, 23(2), 181–199.
- Bello, M. A., Alabi, W. A., & Tawose, A. O. (2015). Impacts of manpower training and development on employees of Bio-Resources Development Centre (BIODEC) of Federal Ministry of Science and Technology, Ogbomosh, Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, 3(2), 57–66.
- Bohorquez Fiano, A. (2022). Improving the sales training program in the Mexican Notebook Company. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 11(3), 32–40.
- Burhan Ismael, N., Jabbar Othman, B., Gardi, B., Abdalla Hamza, P., Sorguli, S., Mahmood Aziz, H., & Anwar, G. (2021). The role of training and development on organizational effectiveness. *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management*, 5(2), 15–24.
- Chanana, N. (2021). Employee engagement practices during COVID-19 lockdown. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 21(4), e2508.
- Downes, A. S. (2022). Best practices of public–private partnerships on education and skills training in the Caribbean. *Caribbean Quarterly of Education and Development*, 44(2), 65–83.
- Elnaga, A., & Imran, A. (2018). The effect of training on employee performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 137–147.
- Hammond, H., & Churchill, R. Q. (2018). The role of employee training and development in achieving organizational objectives: A study of Accra Technical University. *Archives of Business Research*, 6(2), 67–74.
- Herzberg, F. (1966). *Work and the nature of man*. Cleveland, OH: World Publishing.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. B. (1959). *The motivation to work* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- International Survey Research. (2004). *ISR survey report*. ISR Consulting.
- Kaung, S. (2019). Analysis on the impact of training and development on employee productivity in Sabai @ Inya Restaurant in Yangon, Myanmar. *Journal of Management and Training*, 5(1), 12–22.

- Khassawneh, O., & Elrehail, H. (2022). The effect of participative leadership style on employees' performance: The contingent role of institutional theory. *Administrative Sciences, 12*(4), 195.
- Khassawneh, O., Mohammad, T., & Momany, M. T. (2023). Perceived overqualification and job outcomes: The moderating role of manager envy. *Sustainability, 15*(1), 84.
- Khassawneh, O., & Wu, L. (2023). The role of diverse leadership styles in teaching to sustain academic excellence at secondary level. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, 1096151.
- Khtatbeh, M. M., Mahomed, A. S. B., Bin Ab Rahman, S., & Mohamed, R. (2020). The mediating role of procedural justice on the relationship between job analysis and employee performance in Jordan industrial estates. *Heliyon, 6*(10), e05033.
- Obadahun, S. O., Kadir, N. A., & Abu Bakar, M. Z. (2022). Training and development of public university academics in Nigeria and sustainable development goals (SDGs). *African Identities*. Advance online publication.
- Rampa, R., & Agogué, M. (2021). Developing radical innovation capabilities: Exploring the effects of training employees for creativity and innovation. *Creativity and Innovation Management, 30*(1), 211–227.